

Our second Newsletter is out!

Dear Reader,

The last year has been very busy for the SiComb team.

We are happy to share with you the project's second newsletter, where you will find out SiComb's latest developments and future plans.

From the progress of the **transfer process and the CVD reactor to fabricating the 4H-SiCOI stacks and fabricating 4H-, 3C-, and amorphous SiC nano/microdevices**, the **importance of transferring innovation knowledge and experience to create impact focussing on research to business**. The **development of an HFCVD reactor** through the SiComb project has successfully started, and a customized **Thermo-Electric Cooling unit, namely the 'CustomTEC'** has been proposed.

But not only!

In the newsletter, you will **meet our researchers** and find out about the several events we attended.

Find below what we have been up to!

Our 1st IN PERSON Project Meeting!

We are more than happy to share with you this picture of the Team!

Partners met in person in Torino, at Politecnico di Torino, for the first time and it was a fruitful occasion to finally see each other and to talk about the project altogether.

Silicon carbide is emerging rapidly in novel photonic applications thanks to its unique photonic properties facilitated by advances in nanotechnologies such as nanofabrication and nanofilm transfer. SiComb project is developing the first on-chip optical frequency comb made of Silicon Carbide (SiC).

During the intense two-day consortium meeting, the SiComb partners discussed the main achievements and results up to today, while also deciding on the future of the project.

The meeting was a rewarding occasion to brainstorm the next steps in the SiComb project.

More will come in the next months, stay tuned!

Progress of the transfer process and the FAU CVD reactor

Advanced material platforms such as SiC-on-Insulator (SiCOI) stacks are indispensable for the fabrication of high-performance optical devices. As part of the SiComb project, FAU provides such platforms to our project partners based on a self-developed layer transfer technology. Starting from 3C-SiC grown heteroepitaxial on silicon by CVD the silicon is wet chemically removed and the remaining thin 3C-SiC layer is bonded to a suitable substrate material. The substrates used must have a lower index of refraction compared to the 3C-SiC to enhance light confinement and decrease optical losses in the photonic devices. Different substrate materials as well as bonding approaches have been analyzed extensively with respect to their suitability for the transfer process. The best results could be achieved using an adhesive bonding approach in combination with a SiO₂ coated polycrystalline SiC material as substrate. The results were recently presented at the international conference on silicon carbide and related materials (ICSCRM22) in Davos (Switzerland) and have been accepted for publication in Materials Science Forum (TransTech.Publ.).

Image (left): SiOI stack after transfer process with 3C-SiC top layer (yellow) and SiO₂ coated poly SiC substrate (greenish)

Image (right): SEM crosscut of SiCOI stack

The reaction chamber of the employed chemical vapour deposition (CVD) setup has been redesigned. Instead of quartz the susceptor holder was changed to a two-part system consisting of a water-cooled stainless and hydrogen-resistant steel part and an Al₂O₃ ceramic susceptor holder. This ceramic holder is replaceable and doesn't need to be water-cooled during relatively low-temperature growth processes of up to 1200°C. The cracking of the carbon-containing precursor such as C₃H₈ will be improved since the susceptor holder is not water-cooled and therefore exhibits higher temperatures than the original quartz holder. This will cause the reactive gas flux to be pre-heated before reaching the susceptor itself. Furthermore, the adaptability of the whole system is improved since the susceptor holder can be exchanged quickly. To ensure that the material of the new susceptor holder can withstand the high-temperature gradients, numerical simulations have been conducted, covering the temperature field, the magnetic induction and the resulting stress. Furthermore, the gas fluxes in the system have been calculated. One goal in the simulations will be the investigation of the impact of the changed reaction chamber on the resulting SiC layer as well as the examination of new precursor gases such as C₂H₂ or CH₄ to further increase the quality of 3C-SiC epitaxial layers.

New Al₂O₃ ceramic (not water-cooled)

DTU is working on fabricating the 4H-SiCOI stacks and fabricating 4H-, 3C-, and amorphous SiC nano/micro devices

At DTU, we are focusing on simulating the silicon carbide (SiC) optical devices, developing the SiC-on-insulator (SiCOI) stack formation and SiC device nanofabrication processes, and characterizing the performance of the devices. Particularly, we are working on fabricating the 4H-SiCOI stacks and fabricating 4H-, 3C-, and amorphous SiC nano/micro devices.

Image: Researcher mounting a SiC chip for E-beam lithography

Regarding to 4H-SiCOI stack formation, there are two methods generally. One is the ion-cut method, which requires several key steps, including ion implantation, oxidation, bonding, and annealing.

The other method to produce 4H-SiCOI requires key steps of bonding, grinding and polishing, which allows ultra-low loss SiC photonic devices, suitable for the applications, such as frequency comb generation. We have developed a novel SiC bonding process, which is crucial for both formation methods, and we have filed a patent based on this process. We are also investigating and developing lapping and polishing processes for the second method to obtain SiC thin films with low absorption. Regarding SiC device fabrication, we have developed fabrication processes of making 4H-, 3C-, and amorphous SiC nano/micro devices with high performance. Two types of mask materials, i.e. HS and aluminum, are investigated.

HSQ can be used as the lithography resist and the mask, simultaneously. Aluminum must be patterned through an additional lift-off process, with CSAR as the lithography resist. The former process enables tiny structures with smooth sidewall roughness, while the latter process benefits from shorter lithography duration and high etching selectivity. With these efforts, during the past years, we studied the thermal behaviors (<https://doi.org/10.1002/adpr.202100068>, https://doi.org/10.1364/CLEO_AT.2022.JW3B.190) and optical nonlinearity (<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0053296>) of SiC microring resonators and designed and demonstrated photonic devices, including power splitters (<https://doi.org/10.1109/JLT.2022.3169661>) and polarization beam splitters (<https://doi.org/10.1364/PRJ.443543>, <https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.481314>) in SiC integrated platforms. We also contributed to two review papers, one is SiC photonics bridging quantum technology (<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsp Photonics.1c01775>), and the other is an invited paper, novel photonic applications of SiC, which is currently in the press. Meanwhile, we took chances to present our results and enhance the visibility of SiCOMB project in international conferences, including the [XXV AIV Conference in Italy](#) and [Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics \(CLEO\)](#) in the US.

Image: A schematic of frequency comb generation in a SiC microring resonator

In the coming year, we will continue to work on SiC for integrated photonics and nonlinear photonics. A particular effort will be made to evaluate and improve the temperature-controlling setup together with our partner POLITO and experimentally achieve the frequency comb generation in SiC photonic chips. We are also invited to give a tutorial talk at [International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials 2023](#) and participate in Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics 2023.

Impact from research – innovation service by research to business training

Alminica AB is partner in SiComb regarding transfer of innovation knowledge and experience. That will result in increased capacity to create impact. The motivation is driven by that technology should align with European strategies. That will create synergies. The overall aim is to contribute to Green Deal, Sustainable Development Goals, etc. However, these are long-term. The way to move into that direction in practice is by understanding how the project, its value chain, and each partners activity align with the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) that was introduced by the European Commission about ten years ago. This place-based innovation policy concept is about the entrepreneurial discovery process in innovative sectors, fields or technologies. Each partners region has thematic areas of priorities. The synergistic effect is created by understanding how partners know-how and technology align with one or several of the regional thematic areas. Now the Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategy (S4) is emerging. By that the technology and smart specialisation synergy alignment can motivate how they match towards sustainability. Over time the impact progress will align with Sustainable Development Goals.

Image: Smart Specialisation Strategy and Sustainable Smart Specialisation Strategy

This is especially relevant for future emerging technologies, such as those addressed in SiComb. This is an impact approach that strengthens Europe. In such a way EU projects can present how they create impact during the project, and that there is a post-project effect. This knowledge is being transferred to researchers in SiComb by innovation sessions in online mode and will be presented at the physical project meetings. The innovation knowledge has grown into an innovation service that is offered by Alminica about impact creation. All exploitation routes from the research will at some point answer the question: what is the business of your research impact? Therefore, the overall transfer of knowledge to societal impact is given by focussing on research to business. This new innovation service is available at www.researchtobusiness.tech

The HFCVD reactor developed through the SiComb project has successfully started!

To prepare SiC photonic thin films at very low deposition temperatures, typically lower than 800°C, different approaches have been explored such as plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (in collaboration with Plasma-Therm Europe, using a Corial D250 PECVD facility) and physical vapor deposition (PVD). These different deposition processes allow to get SiC thin films with a very wide range of chemical, structural and then optical properties. By adjusting the layer composition -SixCy with or without hydrogen-, its crystallinity -from amorphous to crystalline layers-, both the refractive index and the attenuation coefficient can be customized to meet the photonic device specifications. To go even further in the flexibility and control of the SiC thin film deposition parameters, and especially to probe the 400-800°C temperature range, in which the crystallization of the amorphous films is expected to occur, a hot filament chemical vapour deposition (HFCVD) reactor has been developed. CNRS-SIMaP is very happy to announce that the HFCVD reactor developed through the SiComb project has successfully started. Entirely homemade (design, simulation, fabrication, and tests), the reactor showed outstanding performance. The first SiC thin film deposition tests are scheduled in the coming weeks.

**Image:
HFCVD reactor
3D CAD drawing of the reactor**

**Image:
Camera picture
of the HFCVD reactor**

Politecnico di Torino proposes CustomTEC

Politecnico di Torino (PoliTo) is one of the partner universities in the framework of the SiComb European project. The main PoliTo activities fall within Work Package 2.

In this context, the know-how of PoliTo research group in the field of manufacturing technologies and analysis systems control is applied to two tasks: the temperature control of the SiC device during tests and the processing of the CVD-deposited SiC film. As regards the first one, a customized Thermo-Electric Cooling unit, namely the 'CustomTEC', is proposed. Additive manufacturing is employed for the fabrication of a highly customized holder aiming to perfectly integrate the silicon device with a TEC system. The customized system allows choosing a temperature at which the silicon device must be stabilized to improve its performance. The expected final result is a portable plug-and-play system.

Image: Custom TEC and related controller

As regards the latter, some tests are currently running to introduce the Silicon Carbide Laser Annealing (SiC-LA) in the device fabrication process. The laser annealing of SiC aims to induce a certain reticular order after CVD deposition. Such a process is expected to completely overcome the drawbacks of thermal annealing, which applies up to 1000°C to the whole wafer. Instead, with laser annealing, the reordering heat is expected to be focused only on specific sites in the wafer. The laser annealing of SiC exploits an advanced integrated system where the core is a femtosecond laser with three wavelengths: 343, 515 and 1030 nm. From the first tests, the femtosecond laser in the UV range seems to be the most effective. Further investigations will focus on the structural modification of the material depending on the laser working parameters, as well as on the process environment control in a dedicated process chamber.

SPOTLIGHT

Events

News

Save the Date

Meet the Researchers

To increase its network and visibility over the past year, SiComb has taken part in several events, bringing attention to its innovation among both the scientific community and the general public

A promotional banner for the AIV XXV Conference. It features a blue background on the left with the text "aiv XXV Conference" in white. The center shows an aerial view of a city with a large domed building and a bay. The right side has a light blue background with the text "May 10 - 12 2022" and "Naples, Complesso Monumentale di S. Maria la Nova" with a location pin icon.

aiv
XXV
Conference

May 10 - 12
2022

Naples, Complesso
Monumentale di S. Maria
la Nova

Between 10 and 12 May 2022 the **25th edition of the AIV Conference "Material, Interfaces, Processes in Industrial and Basic Research Application"** took place in Naples (Italy). Project Coordinator Haiyan Ou (Associate Professor at the Technical University of Denmark, DTU) delivered a presentation introducing "SiComb - Developing an innovative chip-based optical frequency comb". SiComb will be therefore presented as a case study of a breakthrough EU project. Partners of the project's consortium were present as well at the XXV AVI Conference, as the Politecnico of Torino - with several scientific contributions related to SiComb - and Moverim Sprl - with a contribution on Horizon Europe opportunities and perspectives.

The three-day Conference was an exceptional multidisciplinary environment!

SiCOMB attended the **International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials (ICSCRM)** on 11-16 September 2022. ICSCRM is the most important technical conference series on silicon carbide (SiC) and related materials. Numerous significant advancements in SiC research as a whole and in the direction of energy-efficient applications were first published and covered at the ICSCRM conference series, and FAU results were presented in this unique context.

The ICSCRM2022 was both inspiring and thrilling!

**19th International Conference
on Silicon Carbide
and Related Materials 2022**

DAVOS, Switzerland

11 - 16 September 2022

Another important event that SiComb attended was the **EIC Summit 2022** which took place on 7-8 December 2022 in Brussels. The key European deep-tech innovation event of the year was bringing together start-ups, researchers, investors, policymakers, and corporates. The EIC Summit 2022 has been a really thrilling moment, addressing several topics aimed at reshaping and strengthening the innovation area in the future.

Indeed, one of the primary drivers of the development of EIC funding opportunities is the emergence of novel technologies. The SiCOMB project was funded by the Horizon 2020 FET-Open (Future and Emerging Technologies) program, which is now a component of the Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder.

During the event the Project's presentation (available in Zenodo and on YouTube) was displayed in front of hundreds of people!

The crisis in the semiconductors supply chain

The crisis in the semiconductors supply chain needs to be urgently addressed, as the consequences of the pandemic before and the war in Ukraine have been affecting Europe's accessibility to these precious components. As a matter of fact, the European Commission has recently recognized this priority, by developing a European Chips Act, which aims to strengthen manufacturing activities, support innovation and reinforce Europe's technological leadership, by adopting a resilient ecosystem approach.

The European Chips Act will support Europe's resilience and competitiveness in semiconductor technologies and applications and aid in the transition to a greener, more digital economy. This will be accomplished by enhancing Europe's technological superiority in the area, addressing the semiconductor shortages, and boosting Europe's technological supremacy. Together with Member States and international partners, it will mobilize more than €43 billion in public and private investments.

The new measures will make Europe a major global player in the semiconductor ecosystem. The new measures will make Europe a major global player in the semiconductor ecosystem.

Chips are crucial assets for industries in various range of sectors and semiconductors are vital for European industry and society Chip supply chains are global, complex, and currently dependent on a small number of manufacturing facilities, making the industry vulnerable to disruptions.

Europe has an overall global semiconductors production market share of less than 10% and is heavily dependent on third-country suppliers in a complex geopolitical context.

The European Union aims to produce 20% of the world's semiconductors by 2030. It is one of the most ambitious goals but extremely needed.

As a project that is developing the first on-chip optical frequency comb made of silicon carbide (SiC), we believe that The Chips Act is a unique chance for Europe to work together across all Member States for the benefit of the entire continent.

In the next months, SiComb will closely monitor the development of the European Chips Act.

Save the Date

WOCSDICE-EXMATEC 2023

You are warmly welcome to the 46th Workshop on Compound Semiconductor Devices and Integrated Circuits held in Europe and the 17th Expert Evaluation and Control of Compound Semiconductor Materials and Technologies ([WOCSDICE-EXMATEC 2023](#)). This edition will be held in Palermo (Italy) and will take place May 21-25th 2023. The event brings together internationally recognized scientists, as well as promising early career researchers and engineers to disseminate state-of-the-art research findings in the areas of compound semiconductor materials, associated devices, and integrated circuits. The presence of multidisciplinary well-known distinguished experts, young and talented researchers, and business delegates from all over the world to present and exchange cutting-edge ideas and technologies in the fields of material fabrication, characterization, and processing of compound semiconductors.

ICSCRM 2023

The International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials gathers the world's foremost experts and leading companies working on Silicon Carbide and related topics.

ICSCRM is an annual scientific event that explores, presents, and discusses the newest achievements in the field of wide-bandgap semiconductors focusing on silicon carbide (SiC) and other wide-bandgap semiconductors. The conference also serves as an international forum for the exchange of ideas on recent scientific and technical issues among researchers and engineers in industrial, academic, and public sectors.

Meet the Researchers

Jana Schultheiß

Field of Expertise: Characterisation of cubic silicon carbide

University: Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Hello, my name is Jana and I am currently working on my PhD at FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg in the field of crystal growth of silicon carbide. Since October 2022, I have been involved in the SiComb project studying cubic silicon carbide employing various characterization methods. My interest in science was already piqued in school through chemistry and during my master's thesis in the field of applied mineralogy, I realized that I wanted to stay in research. Therefore, I chose a research topic that opens many pathways in the future. Working closely with my colleagues, especially on new challenges, is an aspect that I really appreciate about my work. In addition, it is helpful to gain new perspectives on different topics. In the SiComb project, I am looking forward to a good collaboration with partners from academia and industry and hope to gain knowledge from the different disciplines. For the future of our research topic, I hope that cubic silicon carbide will become consistently manufacturable on a large scale to enable its use in existing as well as promising new applications.

Johannes Steiner

Field of Expertise: Vapor phase growth of SiC, numerical simulation

University: Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

I am currently finishing my Ph.D. on dislocations present in hexagonal SiC grown with the help of the physical vapor transport method. During my Ph.D. I learned to love the wide variety of topics covered in the growth of single crystalline materials, including the many methods of crystal growth, the numerical simulation of our various growth setups or the wide variety of ways to characterize crystals and samples. Another intriguing fact about working on a new scientific topic is the freedom to think about a new problem and its many possible solutions. I'm excited to employ my experience of SiC growth in the chemical vapor deposition method and the cubic polytype. The SiComb project hosts many experts in their own respective fields and I'm looking forward to our exchange of ideas. SiC as a material has grown substantially in the last few years in the power electronic field and I'm glad to be able to help expand the utilization of SiC into the topic of photonics. Especially the usage of SOI substrates to facilitate 3C-SiC growth in CVD will be highly interesting and a key part of my research.

Vincent Tabouret

Field of Expertise: Vapor and Plasma growth of SiC and other optical crystal

University: University of Grenoble Alpes

I am currently pursuing a Post Doctorate at Simap laboratory working on the process to make amorphous Silicon Carbide for SiComb. The focus in our lab is to work on the deposition of thin layer with magnetron sputtering at low temperature and establish the link between the different properties of the material. In addition, I work on the development of a new Hot Wire CVD furnace to deposit Silicon Carbide layer by another method. I also test the possibility to polish the thin layer by using chemical or plasma etching. This would allow reducing optical loss on the surface of the photonic devices without indulging any stress in the bulk or the different interfaces. While focused on the deposition and characterization, I am also able to explore diverse topics: theoretical as optical study or thermodynamics; or technical as the assembly of a furnace. Thus, I can work with colleagues coming from various profession and explore the different facet of the research. Their different point of view are very useful and enjoyable when facing the myriad difficulties. I hope the various processes of deposition of silicon carbide will be improved and mastered to benefit from its formidable properties.

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Sicomb

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